

The Image of the Human Psyche in Abdulla Oripov's Poems

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Abstract. In this article, one of the leading representatives of Uzbek literature, It was published after the death of Abdulla Oripov, the poems included in the poetry collection "The Birth of a Poet" describe the mental state of a person, emotional experiences, or values unique to the Uzbek people.

Key words: Human, honesty, uzbek nation, philosopher, spiritual world, mother, hospitable, period, thinking, experience, feelings, situation.

Abdulla Oripov was able to reflect various scenes of people's life and human inner world with his poetry. In Uzbek poetry, he expanded the scope of artistic reflection of the human spiritual world: he poetically explored the human life, the purpose of living, the inner and outer world of man, the social foundations of his existence, and enriched the philosopher with generalizations and discoveries. From the very beginning of his poems, a poet with a beautiful voice entered the field of creativity and came to the attention of great artists (Abdullah Kahhor, Maqsud Shaikhzoda, Azod Sharafidinov), he rose from the ladder of creativity with bold and bold steps, moreover, only the pain of the people. The main principle of the poet was to describe the problems of the time with poetic thinking and philosophical outlook. After the poet's death, his poems from 1957-1965 were collected and published under the name "Birth of the Poet". The poems included in the collection vividly and impressively describe the homeland and patriotism, love, devotion to love, the beautiful hall and the unique nature of the village, it's flora, people, the country, the anthem of the motherland, and the spiritual experiences of the great dreamer and struggler. By reading each poem in this collection, we can feel the creative "me" and the human "me" of the poet, and we will become familiar with the times when Abdula Oripov lived, the emotions he felt, and share in the sorrows and joys of people. His philosophical poetry always reflected the scenes of human psyche and activity. "No matter how beautiful nature is, in any case it is secondary in art. The view that the main subject of art should be a human being" became the main view of poetry. In the poems "To my mother", "Letter", "Shepherd", "Classmate", "Hospitable old man", "To my brother" included in the collection "Birth of the Poet", love and respect for people or the values unique to the Uzbek people are drawn in colored paints. Let's look at the poem "Mother",

Sleepless nights, my immature head

You brought me up with lullaby, Mother!

You held my hand when I walked for the first time,

A kind person who reached the point of happiness.

In the poem "Letter", a child who misses his mother asks the birds to send greetings to his mother:

Birds that flew happily,

Listen to my tune.

Then fly and arrive quickly,

To my mother's house.

Say hello, birds.

Tell your poet son be safe,

It will come sooner or later,

Say he missed so badly

In fiction, the image of birds has acted as a messenger and messenger since time immemorial. For example, Maina in the epic "Ravshan" conveys Hasan Khan's letter to Khan Dalli. Abdulla Oripov also skillfully used the image of birds to illuminate the psychological aspects of the lyrical hero and told the birds about his pains and thoughts and asked him to convey his greetings to his mother.

The poem "Hospitable Old Man" describes how friendly the Uzbek people are to guests, how much they respect guests, using the proverb "A guest is as great as your father" as a program:

Leading a guest from the village street

The old man was coming home.

A car passed by, spitting dust and dirt,

The guest cleared his throat in annoyance.

Then he turned away and touched his clothes,

Father looked at his guest for a while,

Says: - It is easy to clean dusty clothes,

Guest, if your heart is not dusty!

In fact, as described in the poem, it is easy to clean dusty clothes, the dust of the heart and soul is a lifelong, indelible defect. The poet is hardworking and generous in his work,

We are very proud of our motherland, which "places a guest in its heart", "gives its life if a guest asks for a place", "feeds a guest without eating", and is famous for its hospitality. In Abdulla Oripov's lyrics, the Uzbek people and Uzbekistan are observed and interpreted with a unique, unique perspective.

"The poet considered it his duty to express opinions and observations that correspond to the interests of the people, even in a time when artificial ideology ruled and many poets were taught to express their opinions based on certain standards." Disloyal, arrogant, rude, oppressive, boastful people are condemned both in society and in literature. In particular, such a category of people is criticized in the poet's poem "I hate".

I hate rude people

Let me tell you about a teacher.

Don't scare even an owl

He looks so innocent and quiet!

But the mature gentleman is a miser,

Arrogant is, therefore, a hidden tyrant.

He talked about intelligence in class yesterday

He didn't answer to my Hello!

"The poet tries to awaken the consciousness of his contemporaries with images. In each of his poems, A. Oripov strives to penetrate deeper into the spiritual world of his contemporary, to understand his rich and complex feelings and thoughts, and through this to express his attitude to life. "The poem is the voice of the era, and at the same time, in the words of A. Oripov, it is also a "child of need". Every work of the poet was born out of spiritual needs. Images are a means of expression, a picture of this

spiritual need. One of the characteristics of the phenomenon of A. Oripov is his philosophical observations about his contemporaries, his enigmatic behavior, his intelligence, and his secrets. Indeed, the poet sees in his image both a sacrifice of his life for the nation and a weak and helpless subject to enmity and envy."The poem "Philosophy of Life" in the collection describes a deep philosophy of life, a bitter reality of life:

He was standing on the beach.

I'm afraid of water

I wished for medicine for my aching heart.

From someone's dirty laundry

The pains are increasing, the heart is at night...

If he finds it in front of the elder, it is an excuse,

Personal devotion turns outward.

Sometimes he gave a gift, sometimes - a hoof,

Naughty soul was hunted by the end.

It's a time when discipline has weakened in the country

Fortune smiled on him:

Greedy is like a puppet with a greedy hand

He was placed on the throne!

"By showing the tragedy of the world and man, the poet does not want to depress the reader, on the contrary, he wants to warn him, he wants to open the eyes of the soul, he wants to call him to fight against oppression and evil."Truly, the first poems of the poet showed that he considered poetry not as a propagandist of ideology, but as a researcher of the human psyche. He took a place among the great figures of Uzbek national literature with his poems, which are a new form and content of oriental poetry based on superstition, high imagery, humanity and goodness."A. Oripov has such poems in which he likes himself... a poet knows: he cannot explain himself until he likes himself. A poet becomes a poet with a poem or a line that he likes. Neither the poem nor the line that the poet loved will never die. His warmth gives hope to the hopeless, and a remedy to the helpless." The poem "Pain of Conscience" belongs to the category of soul writings:

Take me on my way, guilty conscience,

I will burn in your fire this time.

The memory of my past day is painful.

I have sinned, sinful man.

I have sinned, cut off my tongue,

Tell me, why did you take my freedom away?!

I'm jealous of those who are attractive,

Why did you get lost at that time?

The lyrical hero suffered from the torment of conscience due to his tongue and internal conflict, the fiery torment of conscience does not leave him alone. There are qualities that define a person's humanity and distinguish him from an animal, and this is conscience. If a person's conscience is tormented, if he answers for his actions in front of his own conscience, if he can judge himself and make a judgment, this indicates that his conscience is awake and alive. Through this image, the artist considered the main criteria of his work to portray the pain of the nation, the philosophy of the ancestors, the national values of the Uzbek nation born from the harmony of spirit and thought, the glorification of spiritual virtues, and the condemnation of vices in the heart of the people.

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